

NOVEL FILLER MATERIALS FOR SKIN-STIFFENER STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

To manufacture out-of-plane joints in composite stiffened panels, such as the connection between skin and T, I, omega (hat) shaped stiffeners, a filler material is needed to fill the void between the skin, flanges and web. The most common filler is a unidirectional prepreg tape rolled into a “noodle”, which is not only expensive to fabricate, but also has low strength that can lead to premature failure of the loaded joint. In this paper, eight novel filler concepts are introduced and experimentally validated against the baseline filler (noodle) via T-joint tensile tests. Polyamide nonwoven interleaved joints increase the damage tolerance of the structure at the cost of reduced strength, vertical nanotubes yield no difference, but thermoplastic nonwoven nanofibres increase the failure initiation load by 6%. Additively manufactured fillers have lower strength but demonstrate the possibility of thermoplastic-thermoset hybrid structures. Fillers made of chopped unidirectional and woven prepreg match the strength of the baseline noodle and can serve as a cost-effective replacement. Another low cost, resin infused braided concept has lower strength, but its counterpart made of multiple individual braids has the same strength as the baseline filler. Moreover, the latter concept indicates that different resin systems (infusion and prepreg) can be successfully cured together without causing a knockdown in strength, and can serve as a basis for a new range of novel applications besides out-of-plane joints.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite materials possess great weight saving potential in many applications due to their high relative strength and stiffness. However, thin shell structures need stiffener reinforcements as they are prone to buckling and have low out-of-plane strength. Various profiles can be attached to the laminate to form a stiffened panel, the most common sections used in aerospace structures are T, I, Z, L and hat (omega) sections.

During manufacturing, out-of-plane joints are often co-cured with the skin to improve the integrity of the product and remove the assembly cost and added weight of fasteners. Additionally, composite materials are restrained by manufacturing constraints such as the minimum radius a ply can form. Subsequently, a deltoid shaped void is generated in the junction region of the skin, flanges and web. Such a feature is undesirable in a load-bearing structure and is usually filled with a filler material to eliminate the stress concentrations and ensure the geometrical stability of the joint.

The most commonly used filler, also known as a “noodle”, is manufactured from a manually rolled unidirectional (UD) ply. However, it is labour intensive to manufacture a noodle, and due to its orientation, weak transverse tensile strength and the loading conditions of out-of-plane joints, fillers can be the weakest link in the structural integrity of stiffened panels. Therefore, the search for stronger and more cost-effective fillers has been an important topic in the literature over recent years [1].

3D woven and braided fillers can be used to increase the strength of the joint and eliminate the need for rolling during manufacturing. In one example, the initial failure load of T-joints with braided fillers subjected to tensile loading was increased by 36% compared to the conventional rolled

specimens [2]. The main drawbacks of this method are the restrictions of resin infusion processes and possible insufficient compaction of the filler during cure. Thermoplastic and foam fillers can be injection moulded, but this procedure needs the additional step of machining of the filler to its final geometry [3]. Through-the-thickness reinforcements such as pinning and stitching can greatly enhance the strength and damage tolerance of the joint, but the manufacturing time and cost are increased significantly [4]. Interleaving the joint with nonwoven veils can also increase its mechanical performance. Wang and Soutis [5] reported a 44% increase in ultimate tensile strength of a T-joint interleaved with polyester veils compared to a pristine one, but this method is also limited to resin infusion. A cost-effective manufacturing process is pultrusion, but this requires the in-situ curing of the whole stiffener section and therefore it cannot be used for manufacturing individual fillers to be assembled later in a prepreg structure [6].

In this paper, eight novel concepts are introduced to increase the strength of fillers and out-of-plane joints or reduce their manufacturing time and cost: 1) interleaving the joint with polyamide nonwoven mat, 2) vertically aligned nanotubes and 3) nonwoven nanofibre interleaves. Then, 4) a 3D printed thermoplastic filler and fillers made of 5) chopped UD and 6) woven chips are proposed. Finally, two combinations of resin infused braided fillers 7-8) and prepreg joints are presented. The new concepts are implemented in a T-joint and tested under tensile loading. The results are compared with a T-joint containing a baseline filler (manually rolled UD noodle).

2 MANUFACTURE OF BASELINE JOINT AND EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The manufacturing of the 6 baseline specimens is introduced in detail in [7] and is only described briefly in this work. The manufacturing of the 3 specimens used for each of the novel concepts are based on the same procedure and their distinct features are outlined in section 3.

The geometry and the boundary conditions of the tensile test are shown in Fig. 1. Hexcel HexPly® AS4/8552 UD prepreg [8] was used with a nominal cured ply thickness (CPT) of 0.196 mm. The stacking sequence of the skin and overlaminates were $[90/45/0/-45]_{3s}$ and $[90/45/0/-45]_{2s}$, respectively, where 0° is aligned in the Z direction. The plies are referred to as Ply 1 to Ply 16 in the overlamine, with Ply 1 being adjacent to the filler (0°).

Figure 1: Specimen geometry and test setup

The baseline filler was manufactured by manually rolling a ply with the same cured cross-sectional area of the theoretical deltoid shape. Then, it was placed in a noodle forming tool and debulked. The steel tool used for curing consisted of two overlamine tools and a caul plate for the skin. The sublaminates were debulked after laying up every 4 plies. To ensure the consistent temperature

distribution during curing, the lowest allowable heat up and cool down rates were chosen according to the manufacturer's datasheet [8].

After curing, the individual samples were cut and surfaces were ground to P2500 quality.

The specimens were annealed before testing to eliminate the moisture content accumulated after manufacturing. The tests were carried out at 2 mm/min crosshead displacement rate and at room temperature with an Instron 3369 machine. Deformation in the vicinity of the fillers was recorded with high-speed cameras and displacement was taken as the crosshead displacement of the Instron machine.

3 MANUFACTURE OF THE ALTERNATIVE CONCEPTS

3.1 Interleaved joints

Delamination of the interface of the filler and the adjacent ply, or within the laminate in an out-of-plane joint is one of the most common failure mechanisms of stiffeners [1]. A common method to increase the delamination strength is to interleave the plies with a toughening material [9]. In this work, three concepts are investigated: use of a polyamide (PA) nonwoven mat, a layer of vertical nanotubes, and a nonwoven nanofibre mat combined with a baseline filler.

Nonwoven mats are not intended to be used with prepregs due to the fixed resin content of the latter. To evaluate their behaviour embedded in a prepreg laminate, double cantilever beam (DCB) and end notched flexure (ENF) tests were carried out on several nonwoven mats to characterise their mode I and II fracture toughnesses. The results, which are not included here, indicated the most significant performance improvement of the Cerex PBN-II® 30100 PA mat (Cerex Advanced Fabrics Inc., referred to as "PA" in this paper) with 0.2 mm dry thickness and 34 gsm weight [10], which was chosen for this study accordingly. One layer of the mat was placed between the filler and Ply 1 in the radius, in the midplane of the web and flanges and under the filler (Fig. 2a) during the assembly of the T-joint.

Reinforcing the interface of two adjacent plies with vertical nanotubes can increase the toughness and durability of the laminate [11]. The 0° plies in the midplanes of the T-joint (Ply 1 in the overlamine and top ply of the skin) were treated with N12 NanoStitch® nanotubes and the joint was manufactured as mentioned above.

The third concept involved the interleaving of all interfaces within the laminate in the vicinity of the radius and skin around the filler with a 4.5 gsm Xantu.Layr® (Revolution Fibres Ltd., [12]) thermoplastic nonwoven nanofibre mat (Fig. 2b). Unlike the PA mat, this interleaf has virtually zero thickness and is developed to be used with prepreg materials.

Figure 2: Location of interleaves in the T-joint: a) PA and NanoStitch® b) Xantu.Layr®

3.2 3D printed thermoplastic filler

The concept presented in this work is a 3D printed thermoplastic filler, co-cured with the epoxy matrix based laminate of the T-joint.

In order to co-cure a thermoplastic filler with the thermoset laminate and implement it in an out-of-plane joint, the material needs to meet three requirements. First, it must have higher melting temperature than the cure temperature of the thermoset resin in the laminate (180 °C), otherwise the

geometry could not be retained during the curing of the joint. Second, the thermoplastic material must be compatible with the thermoset resin to provide sufficient bonding strength. Third, the 3D printed material should have comparable or higher yield strength than the transverse tensile strength of the thermoset composite material.

To the authors' best knowledge, only polyetherimide (PEI) has been demonstrated in the literature to meet the second criterion, i.e. to be compatible with epoxy thermoset resins [13]. Therefore, ULTEM™ 1010 polyetherimide was chosen as material in this work. According to the manufacturer's datasheet [14], the longitudinal tensile strength is 56 MPa. This and the transverse tensile strength were evaluated by the authors with 5 repeats of dog bone tensile tests in both planes based on [15], and the measured values were found to be 64 MPa and 55 MPa, respectively.

The 3D printed filler had the same dimensions as described in section 2 and was printed with 0.1 mm nominal voxel size with an in-house built fused deposition modelling (FDM) printer. Extruder temperature, bed temperature and print speed were set up according to the manufacturer's recommendations [14]. Then, the filler was annealed to eliminate the thermal stresses accumulated during printing. Finally, the 3D printed filler was deburred, assembled and cured within the T-joint assembly according, to section 2.1.

3.3 Chopped fillers

The manufacturing cost of fillers can be reduced by using wastage material left behind from ply cutting and replacing the manual noodle forming step with an automated process. The following solution is a filler made of UD and woven prepreg chips and injected into a forming tool. However, as this is a proof of concept, the latter step was replaced by manual cutting and assembly in this work.

Hexcel HexPly® AS4/8552 material was used for the UD chips and Hexcel HexForce™ AGP280-5H [16] was used for the woven chips. The latter consists of the same AS4 fibres [17] and 8552 resin [8] but has a 5 harness satin woven structure and CPT of 0.29 mm. In theory, the chip size should be as small as possible so that the mechanical behaviour of the filler approaches isotropic; but large enough so that the fibre length is larger than the critical fibre length. Based on preliminary trials, a 5x5 mm chip size was chosen for both cases, as smaller pieces of UD prepreg fell apart during handling. After cutting the same volume of prepreg material as required for the baseline filler, the chips were placed into the noodle forming tool, debulked, and finally assembled within the T-joint (Fig. 3a). After curing and cutting, the specimens were CT scanned to measure the porosity.

Figure 3: Underside view of fillers before the assembly of the overlaminates and the skin: a) chopped UD b) single braided c) multiple braided

3.4 Braided fillers

The proposed concept combines commercially available braided fillers with the pre-impregnated laminate of the T-joint. Unlike conventional noodles, which require labour intensive in-situ rolling and forming during the manufacturing of the stiffeners, the dry braids can be infused and stored in a freezer, independently from the assembly, greatly reducing the manufacturing time of the structure.

Two different fillers were manufactured from Eurocarbon's commercially available product line [18]: one made of a single braid having 28.3 mm² cross-sectional area (referred to as "single braided" in this paper) and one made of eight smaller braids having a total of 28.8 mm² cross-sectional area (referred to as "multiple braided" in this paper). These correlate with the theoretical 27.5 mm² cured cross-sectional area of the rolled noodle. The latter method was implemented to reduce the resin rich

zones and poor compaction of the single braid noodle reported in the literature [19]. Hexcel HexFlow® RTM 6 thermoset resin [20] was used for the infusion, which has the same cure temperature as 8552. After removal from the noodle forming tool, the fillers were assembled (Fig. 3b-c) and cured within the joint according to section 2. Porosity was measured via CT scanning.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Manufactured specimens

Micrographs of the typical cross-sections of the manufactured baseline and proposed fillers can be seen in Fig. 4-5. In the baseline joint (Fig. 4), the skin is flat under the filler and its geometry is virtually identical to the theoretical one. For detailed discussion on the quality of the baseline filler, the authors refer to [7].

Figure 4: Micrograph of the manufactured baseline filler

The PA nonwoven interleaved, NanoStitch® vertical nanotube interleaved and Xantu.Layr® nonwoven nanofibre interleaved specimens can be seen in Fig. 5a-c. The PA layer significantly increased the thickness of the interface between the filler and Ply 1, but its thickness is inconsistent in some locations due to its nonwoven nature. At a higher magnification, the inconsistency of the fibre volume ratio can also be seen. The NanoStitch® vertical nanotubes are not visible even at 50x magnification, whereas the Xantu.Layr® veils are distinguishable from the pristine interfaces of the baseline specimen but resulted in insignificant thickening of the laminate.

Only after cutting the specimens with 3D printed filler was it revealed that in certain cross-sections along the length of the filler, the printer incorrectly printed the layers and gaps appeared inside the middle of the deltoid (bright areas in Fig. 5d). It is assumed to be in connection with the printing parameters, the code generated for printing and the capabilities of the 3D printer. Achieving higher quality should be possible with an industrial grade printer and by fine-tuning the printing parameters. Nevertheless, the geometry of the filler surface is satisfactory as the thermoset resin filled the uneven surface caused by the presence of discrete steps of the layers, ensuring a smooth transition of Ply 1 of the overlaminates from the skin to the web.

The chopped UD and woven fillers are shown in Fig. 5e-f. The width and height of the fillers were higher compared to the theoretical shape, and therefore, as the filler volume was fixed, the ply thickness was increased in the radius and the skin under the filler became non-flat. During manufacturing, the filler forming tool was filled up with chips being generally parallel to the skin or rotated along the Z-axis. This caused a marginally increased resin-rich zone near the top edge of the filler, and lack of chips being parallel to the X-Y-plane. The CT scan revealed <0.1% porosity content in both concepts, but this is within the boundaries of the maximum of 2.5% allowable void content in aircraft components [21].

The single and multiple braided fillers can be seen in Fig. 5g-h. Similarly to the chopped concepts, the width of the multiple braided fillers increased, as well as the ply thickness in the radius. Contrarily, the single braided filler had superior compaction and retained its geometry with significantly less resin-rich areas within it. The reason for this is that the multiple braided fillers contain 8 individual braids which are less resistant to the applied pressure and resin movement in the joint during curing, whereas the single braided fillers have higher integrity and can withstand the acting forces on them more sufficiently. Based on the CT scan analysis, the braided fillers did not contain any voids.

Figure 5: Micrographs of the manufactured fillers: a) PA nonwoven interleaved b) NanoStitch® vertical nanotube interleaved c) Xantu.Layr® nonwoven nanofibre interleaved d) 3D printed e) chopped UD f) chopped woven g) single braided h) multiple braided

4.2 Test results and failure mechanisms

Due to the large number of specimens, only one typical load-displacement curve of each concept is presented (Fig. 6), and the complete list of initial failure loads can be found in Table 1. Micrographs of the failed specimens are shown in Fig. 7-8.

Figure 6: Typical load-displacement curves of the experimental tests

Concept	ID	Initial failure load [N]	Average (SD) [N]	Difference [%]
Baseline	A1	3907	4366 (330)	-
	A2	4818		
	A3	4147		
	A4	4235		
	A5	4560		
	A6	4527		
PA	IA1	3257	3257 (440)	-25%
	IA2	2809		
	IA3	3687		
NanoStitch®	N1	4208	4384 (223)	0%
	N2	4308		
	N3	4635		
Xantu.Layr®	X1	4601	4627 (136)	+6%
	X2	4506		
	X3	4775		
3D printed	P1	2603	2510 (278)	-43%
	P2	2197		
	P3	2730		
Chopped UD	CU1	4507	4589 (106)	+5%
	CU2	4709		
	CU3	4552		
Chopped woven	CW1	4107	4112 (343)	-6%
	CW2	4457		
	CW3	3771		
Single braided	VS1	3924	3401 (1118)	-22%
	VS2	2052		
	VS3	4226		
Multiple braided	VM1	4723	2510 (422)	+2%
	VM2	3984		
	VM3	4705		

Table 1: Test results. Load-displacement curves of the specimens in bold are shown in Fig. 6

Figure 7: Micrograph of the failed baseline filler. For interpretation of the load-displacement curve, see Fig. 6

Five baseline specimens (A1-A4 and A6) had similar failure initiation. After the linear stage during load-up a crack initiated in the radius, triggering the first drop in the load-displacement curve (Fig. 7 point A). This was followed by either one or more cracks in the laminate or the crack of the filler (Fig. 7 point B). The filler crack propagated from the surface of the filler down to the skin and caused delamination along the surface of the filler and under the filler. The laminate of specimen A5 remained intact and its filler cracked first.

The PA interleaved joints all had a filler crack as the first failure event (Fig. 8a, point A) at average of 25% lower load than the baseline joints. The reason for this knockdown is probably the insufficient infusion of the dry mat by the resin during curing. With consistent fibre distribution in the mat and lower interface thickness, it is possible that the drop in interface strength could be mitigated. Similarly to the baseline joints, the crack propagated down to the skin and triggered delamination on the filler surface up to the web, but could not cause delamination immediately under the filler and the joint withstood further loading. Finally, the skin interface failed (Fig. 8a, point B) and started delaminating. However, the improved damage tolerance can be seen in Fig. 6, as the joint absorbed a high amount of energy and carried about 2000 N load during skin delamination, whereas most other joints could only take approximately 500 N following initial failure.

The NanoStitch® interleaved joints showed similar behaviour to the baseline joints both in terms of failure mechanisms (Fig. 8b, point A and B referring to radius laminate and filler crack, respectively) and average initial failure load (<1% difference). As the initial failure did not occur in the filler-laminate surface, the NanoStitch® layer could not change the failure behaviour in this location. However, the nanotube forest across the skin-overlamine interface did not alter the failure mechanism during the delamination of the skin either. To make up for the more complex manufacturing procedure, a significant performance improvement would be needed to consider this concept as a viable solution. It is also possible that the nanotubes work better with toughened resin (such as TC350-1 in [11]), but are not able to improve the properties of the 8552 resin used here.

The Xantu.Layr® interleaved specimens reached the highest average initial failure load of all proposed concepts (6% higher than baseline, which is significant, based on one-sided T-test analysis). The failure mechanisms were similar to the ones occurring in the baseline joints as the overlamine cracked first in case of X1 and X2 specimens (Fig. 8c, point A). However, further cracks occurred in the laminate (Fig. 8c, point B), followed by the final filler crack (Fig. 8c, point C) and sudden drop in load. X3 specimen failed with the filler crack as the first sign of damage initiation. The increased interlaminar strength of the laminate is reflected in the increased overall joint strength. Therefore, this solution can be applied in highly loaded regions of components where the strength improvement outweighs the marginal increase in manufacturing complexity.

The 3D printed fillers suffered from manufacturing defects (see previous section). This was reflected in the results as all joints failed initially with cracking of the filler (Fig. 8d, point A) at 57% lower average initial failure load compared to the baseline concept. In specimen P1, the laminate remained intact, whereas in P2 and P3 specimens it was followed delaminations in the overlamine. However, because of the high fracture toughness of the thermoplastic material, the filler crack could not reach the skin immediately and the joint absorbed more energy before the filler-skin interface

failed (Fig. 8d, point B). Despite the lower strength of the joints, the interface of Ply 1 of the overlamine and the 3D printed filler did not fail in any cases. This proves that the cohesion between the thermoset 8552 and the thermoplastic PEI materials is sufficient for structural applications.

Figure 8: Micrographs of the failed fillers: a) PA nonwoven interleaved b) NanoStitch® vertical nanotube interleaved c) Xantu.Layr® nonwoven nanofibre interleaved d) 3D printed e) chopped UD f) chopped woven g) single braided h) multiple braided. For interpretation of the load-displacement curves see Fig. 6

Chopped UD and woven joints initially failed with radius delaminations at 4589 N and 4112 N average loads, respectively (Fig. 8e-f, points A). These correspond to +5% and -6% difference

compared to the baseline filler. However, the failure of the chopped fillers (Fig. 8e-f, points B) was different from the failure of the rolled noodles. In the case of the baseline concept, the noodle fails because its low transverse tensile strength cannot withstand the loads acting on it as the radius tries to open. The crack then propagates down to the skin without any significant resistance. In the case of the chopped fillers, most of the inside surfaces (filler side) of Ply 1 in the overlamine are covered with chips following the curvature of the ply. This provides protection from the opening mechanism of the radius. Therefore, the crack can only initiate at the end of a chip (“chip drop”) where the resin is accumulated (Fig. 8f). Then the crack propagates along the surfaces of the chips until reaching the other side of the filler and delaminating the skin from the flanges. Subject to the achievable level of automated manufacturing procedure, chopped fillers are feasible solutions to replace the currently utilised rolled UD noodles.

In all cases of the single and multiple braided specimens, the joints failed in the filler (Fig. 8g-h, points A) and the overlamine remained undamaged. The average initial failure loads were 3401 N and 4471 N respectively, corresponding to -22% and +2% difference compared to the baseline concepts. It is notable that VS2 specimen failed at 2052 N, which is the lowest initial failure load of the 30 specimens tested, and VM2 failed at 3984 N, which also an outlier. These can be accounted for the variability of the cross section geometry across the length of the noodle. Due to the non-0° orientation of the braided fibres, the crack could not propagate directly to the skin and had to change its direction several times while developing smaller cracks. In some cases, the skin delamination was delayed by almost horizontal cracking of the bottom of the filler (Fig. 8g, until point B). The main difference between the single and multiple braided specimens was the location of the first crack in the filler. In the first case, it started closer to the top edge of the deltoid, and in the latter case, it started at a similar location as in the case of the baseline noodle. This is probably because the multiple braided fillers have fibres oriented closer to 0° than the fibres in the single braided filler. As the interface of Ply 1 and the filler did not fail, it is demonstrated that curing together an infusion resin (RTM6) and prepreg resin (8552) can provide sufficient strength in the structure. With the reduced cost of the proposed manufacturing procedure, resin infused braided fillers are a highly favourable choice to replace conventional rolled noodles.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Eight novel filler concepts were introduced to increase the strength of composite out-of-plane joints or decrease the manufacturing cost and time of their filler. The new solutions were manufactured as part of a T-joint, tested under tensile loading and compared with the baseline rolled UD filler material.

The results demonstrated that PA nonwoven interleaves can increase the damage tolerance of the joint even if manufactured as part of a prepreg laminate, but they reduce the strength of the interface at the same time. NanoStitch® vertical nanotubes did not change the behaviour of the joint in this specific application. Xantu.Layr® nonwoven nanofibre veils increased the initial failure load of the joints by 6% and can be used as a promising solution in highly loaded components.

Additively manufactured fillers suffered from manufacturing defects and subsequent drop in strength, but showed that the cohesion between the thermoset and thermoplastic resins is sufficiently strong and the weakest link in hybrid components is not the bimaterial interface. With optimised printing parameters and the application of high strength, high temperature and epoxy compatible thermoplastic resins, 3D printed fillers can replace the labour intensive rolled noodles.

Fillers manufactured from chopped UD and woven chips produced essentially the same strength as the baseline filler (+5% and -6% in comparison). With further development in the manufacturing procedure, such as using waste material and automated cutting and injection moulding of the chips, this concept can become a high production rate alternative of currently used noodles.

Finally, braided fillers consisting of resin infused single and multiple braids cured together with the prepreg laminate of the T-joint were manufactured and tested. Whereas the single braided concept failed at 22% lower load than the baseline, the multiple braided filler was 2% stronger. Additionally, all specimens failed without delaminating the interface of the laminate and the filler, which demonstrates that the different infusion and prepreg resins formed a strong bond. This means that resin infused fillers can not only match the strength of the UD rolled fillers, but also significantly reduce the

manufacturing cost and time of out-of-plane joints.

The new solutions introduced in this paper can be used to increase the strength, reduce the manufacturing time and reduce the cost of composite out-of-plane joints. Moreover, the radical concept of hybridising thermoset and thermoplastic resins, and different type of thermoset resins within the same structure and in the same cure cycle opens up a wide range of new applications involving the combination of thermoplastic, infused braided, 3D woven and thermoset prepreg materials.

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